

1 **Imprints of Body-Movement Timing onto Subsequent Processing of Musical**
2 **Rhythm**

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32

Abstract

33 Music often entrains rhythmic body movement (e.g., dancing, locomotion). In turn,
34 body-movement can also shape rhythm processing. Although this phenomenon is often
35 leveraged in music learning, the behavioural and brain processes underlying
36 movement-driven perceptual plasticity remain understudied. This registered report
37 aimed at capturing these processes using electroencephalography (EEG) and hand
38 clapping to an auditory rhythm (derived from West/Central African musical traditions),
39 tested with African-enculturated participants. Neural and behavioural measures were
40 conducted separately, both before vs. after a body-movement session, which primed
41 different metrical interpretations through stepping and clapping along with the stimulus
42 (either three-beat or four-beat metre, the latter being conventionally associated with
43 this rhythm in the participants' culture). Behavioural data showed a propensity to clap
44 the primed metre to a greater extent after vs. before the movement session, indicating
45 that short-term motor engagement can shape rhythmic behaviour beyond cultural
46 experience. In contrast, EEG data did not show corresponding enhancement of neural
47 responses, suggesting that a single brief movement session may not be sufficient as a
48 short-term learning experience to stabilise a metre representation that can be
49 reactivated automatically (i.e., without an explicit, related task). Nonetheless,
50 participants were able to draw upon such short-term learning of metre–rhythm
51 associations to guide movement timing when required to produce overt movement to
52 such a rhythm. Together, these results highlight the interplay of motor engagement,
53 multisensory integration, and cultural experience in shaping rhythm perception.

54 *Keywords:* music cognition; cultural experience; rhythmic entrainment; beat and
55 meter perception; sensorimotor synchronisation; body movement; EEG; frequency
56 tagging

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59 **Foreword**

60 This study is part of a larger programmatic registered report aiming to capture
61 direct neuroscientific evidence for the shaping of auditory information by the pace of
62 previous movements with a cross-cultural perspective (Guérin et al., 2024). Specifically,
63 West/Central African- and European-enculturated individuals were tested in two
64 distinct studies, to demonstrate the culture-driven neural plasticity in rhythm
65 processing in humans. Each study was intended to test a set of specific intra-cultural
66 hypotheses, and the two data sets were also combined to examine a series of
67 cross-cultural hypotheses. The present study reports findings from the
68 African-enculturated participant group.

69 **Introduction**

70 Animals commonly rely on rhythmic movements to explore their environment,
71 which facilitates the sampling of sensory information (Gibson, 1962; Zalta et al., 2020).
72 This so-called ‘active sensing’ process is easily conceivable in the context of vision,
73 somatosensation, or olfaction, where eye, finger, or sniffing movements directly
74 contribute to sensory exploration. In the scope of audition, the way movement might
75 shape perception is less straightforward. This is especially true in species who do not
76 use echolocation as a main sensory system, such as humans, in whom the degree to
77 which such an active sensing process is used to regulate and facilitate sensory inflow –
78 thereby optimising sensitivity to external sounds – remains unclear (Schroeder et al.,
79 2010). This registered report aims to capture how the pace of body movements leaves
80 its imprint on the subsequent processing of auditory information in humans. It
81 capitalises on the intrinsic interplay between music and body movement, and related
82 processes of multisensory integration (i.e., audition, vision, and proprioception).

83 Music has accompanied human activities since the dawn of time (Brown, 2022;
84 Garfinkel, 2018; Vander Elst et al., 2023). Specifically, musical rhythm provides an
85 anchor to time movements through its often highly recurrent temporal structure, a

86 process referred to as *sensorimotor synchronisation* (Repp, 2005; Repp & Su, 2013).
87 This temporal coordination between a rhythmic movement and external auditory
88 rhythm is underpinned by anticipatory mechanisms that allow individuals to estimate
89 future acoustic onsets and apply online adjustments if necessary (Cannon, 2021;
90 van der Steen & Keller, 2013; Vuust & Witek, 2014; Vuust et al., 2022).

91 To be able to form temporal expectancies when listening to music, individuals
92 need to transform complex auditory or other sensory (e.g., visual; Su, 2016) rhythmic
93 inputs into an internal representation of musical-event timing (Cannon, 2021; Large &
94 Palmer, 2002; van der Weij et al., 2017; Vuust et al., 2018). This internal representation
95 typically takes the form of a metre, which corresponds to a nested set of felt pulsations
96 that are often periodic (Lenc et al., 2021; London, 2012; Vuust and Witek, 2014; of
97 note, in the current study, ‘metre’ is used as a comprehensive term with no explicit
98 specification about the number of pulse layers, thus minimising underlying
99 assumptions). Importantly, the metre perceived when experiencing a given rhythm is
100 not driven by the input in a one-to-one fashion. In other words, the perceptual system
101 does not simply search for an internal periodic template that provides the closest match
102 to periodicities marked by the arrangement of prominent acoustic events over time.
103 Rather, meter perception can be considered a form of perceptual categorisation (Lenc
104 et al., 2025), thus relying on a flexible mapping between a rhythmic sensory input and
105 an internal representation of periodic pulses (Iversen et al., 2009; Repp, 2010; Schaefer
106 et al., 2011). Arguably, this mapping is far from trivial, especially when the sensory
107 input lacks unambiguous periodic arrangement of salient acoustic features – as in
108 so-called syncopated (Witek, 2017) or contrametric (Kolinski, 1973) rhythms, where
109 rhythmic and metric structures show a degree of incongruency, which are typical for
110 numerous genres of popular, groove-based music around the world (e.g., jazz, funk,
111 breakbeat, Afro-Cuban, and African styles; Huron & Ommen, 2006; London et al.,
112 2017; Temperley, 1999, 2000). In these specific cases, metre perception must rely on
113 internal processes beyond mere detection of acoustic periodicities in the relevant
114 temporal range (Lenc et al., 2021; London, 2012). One of these processes is the learned

115 *association* between contextual cues (e.g., particular rhythmic figure, timbre, tempo,
116 and social setting) and a specific internal metre (Kaplan et al., 2022; London, 2012;
117 London et al., 2017; van der Weij et al., 2017).

118 Several theoretical models have been proposed to describe the nature of
119 associations between a rhythmic figure (i.e., a temporal pattern of acoustic, visual or
120 proprioceptive events) and an internal metre. These models emphasise to different
121 degrees the role of active body movement in learning to map a particular rhythmic
122 stimulus onto an internal representation of a particular metre. For instance, the
123 predictive-coding theory of music claims that when listening to music, the brain deploys
124 a predictive model (based on prior experience) that guides our perception (Vuust et al.,
125 2018, 2022). Movement production would allow to form highly-precise predictions of
126 auditory event sequences due to the combination of the rhythmic input with multiple
127 sensory information (e.g., proprioceptive and visual inputs; Manning & Schutz, 2015;
128 Wing et al., 2010). Another prominent model, the neural resonance theory, proposes
129 metre perception to emerge due to synchronisation between a given rhythmic stimulus
130 and the intrinsic dynamics of endogenous oscillatory brain networks (Large & Kolen,
131 1994; Large & Snyder, 2009; Large et al., 2023). Notably, according to this theoretical
132 model, oscillatory interactions between the auditory and motor areas of the brain would
133 be crucial for metre perception to arise (Large et al., 2015; Tichko et al., 2021).

134 Also suggesting an effect of movement-related processes on metre perception, the
135 active sensing framework states that the motor system modulates the cortical
136 processing of auditory information by refining attention surrounding relevant sensory
137 information (Morillon et al., 2014, 2015). Specifically, motor delta oscillations (0.5–4
138 Hz) would sharpen the brain processing of rhythmic sounds by synchronising the
139 temporal fluctuations of attention with the timing of auditory events (Morillon et al.,
140 2019; Zalta et al., 2020). More radically, the action simulation for auditory prediction
141 (ASAP) hypothesis proposes that the simulation of periodic movement shapes metre
142 perception (Patel & Iversen, 2014; Proksch et al., 2020). According to this hypothesis,
143 cortical motor planning regions would be entrained by an implicit and automatic

144 process of movement simulation triggered by rhythmic sounds, and this oscillatory
145 pattern would propagate to auditory areas, influencing the metric interpretation of
146 rhythm (Iversen et al., 2009). Although these theoretical models of musical rhythm
147 perception diverge in a number of ways (e.g., anatomical substrates, directionality of
148 relationship between movement and meter perception), they can be viewed as mutually
149 reinforcing (e.g., by describing mechanisms at the brain level or at the cognitive level;
150 see Large et al., 2023; Zalta et al., 2024); and importantly, each of them presupposes a
151 strong role of motor production in metre perception.

152 The effect of body-movement pace on the subsequent internal representation of
153 rhythm has been reported in several empirical studies using behavioural methods. For
154 example, both active and passive body movement coordinated with a rhythmic pattern
155 according to a specific metre was found to bias the way individuals subsequently
156 perceive a rhythm, possibly through vestibular-mediated processes (Phillips-Silver &
157 Trainor, 2008; Trainor et al., 2009). Specifically, both adults and infants have been
158 shown to develop increased expectancy of salient sounds at those positions within a
159 rhythmic pattern that were aligned with the metre the individual had previously moved
160 to (Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007; Su & Pöppel, 2012). However, the behavioural
161 measures used in these studies only constitute an indirect way to capture the internal
162 representation of metre elicited by a rhythm (Lenc et al., 2021). Convergent evidence
163 across various forms of measurements (e.g., measurements of both the neural and
164 behavioural responses as recorded in separate sessions in response to rhythmic stimuli)
165 could thus help moving a significant step toward a comprehensive understanding of how
166 movement can shape the internal representation of metre. One neuroimaging study
167 found that the neural responses to a rhythmic pattern were significantly bolstered after
168 body-movement production, selectively at frequencies related to the metre that
169 participants had moved to (Chemin et al., 2014). However, the rhythmic stimulus used
170 in this study contained prominent metre-related periodicities in its acoustic structure,
171 thus making it hard to disentangle effects driven by an actual internal representation of
172 metre from effects related to low-level sensory processing of the rhythmic input.

173 To move a critical step forward, the objective of this study was to capture direct
174 neuroscientific evidence for the shaping of auditory information by the pace of previous
175 movement. Ecological plausibility was ensured by a cultural congruence between the
176 stimulus and the participant sample. If significant, the effect of short-term prior
177 experience of rhythmic body movements would thus likely be intrinsically supported by
178 a number of distinct processes, including motor planning, visual, auditory,
179 somatosensory and vestibular cues combined together (Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2008;
180 Trainor et al., 2009). Movement-related shaping of auditory information processing was
181 purposely adopted in the current study (a) for its ecological validity in music and dance
182 contexts, and (b) to increase the likelihood of eliciting an effect in the listening block
183 subsequent to the movement priming, due to the mixture of multisensory effects
184 expected to strengthen carry-over effects. Hence, our objective was *not* to define the
185 necessary and sufficient mechanism for the effect of movement on rhythm perception to
186 take place, but rather to capture the brain processes underlying this holistic effect,
187 while not precluding mental imagery of beat or priming by auditory inputs (as in Nave
188 et al., 2022) that could also significantly shape auditory information.

189 **Research Hypotheses**

190 This article is part of a larger programmatic registered report (Guérin et al.,
191 2024), which proposed two distinct but complementary studies to address broad
192 research questions – and thus resulted in two Stage 2 articles. Specifically, this Stage 2
193 article targeted African-enculturated individuals, while another Stage 2 focused on
194 European-enculturated individuals and the cross-cultural comparisons.

195 In the present study, one group of African-enculturated individuals participated
196 in a ~15-min body-movement session consisting of stepping and clapping to a rhythm in
197 synchrony with an overlaid drum sound indicating a three-beat metrical interpretation
198 of the rhythm. Another group of African-enculturated individuals engaged in the same
199 protocol but following a four-beat metrical interpretation of the same rhythm. The
200 rhythmic input consisted of a context-free version of a rhythmic pattern spanning 12
201 elements often used in musical traditions from West to Central Africa (Agawu, 2006;

202 Kubik, 2010; Poole, 2018), and variously referred to as Bembé or standard bell pattern.
203 Specifically, this rhythm often serves as a temporal reference in African (and
204 African-derived) music (Agawu, 2006; Kubik, 2010; Locke, 1982; Polak, 2026; Poole,
205 2018; Toussaint, 2003). While empirical evidence is still lacking, ethnomusicological
206 work suggests that widespread metric mode among populations enculturated in West
207 and Central African musical environments is to experience 12-element rhythmic
208 patterns as suggesting a four-beat metre (Agawu, 2006; Locke, 1982; Poole, 2018). This
209 mode is relatively less prominent in populations enculturated with Euro-American
210 popular or art music traditions. By contrast, individuals with such backgrounds often
211 carry metric modes that would map the same 12-element rhythms to a three-beat metre
212 (Blacking, 1967).

213 The neural activity of participants was recorded using EEG while they stayed
214 still and listened to the same rhythmic input in two sessions directly preceding and
215 following the body-movement session. At the end of each EEG session, participants
216 were asked to clap along with the rhythm as an ecological index of behavioural
217 entrainment to the perceived metre (for a discussion on the importance of using
218 ecological behaviours in timing research, see Rose et al., 2021). A frequency-tagging
219 approach was used to measure the relative prominence of the periodicity corresponding
220 to the perceived metre in the signal of interest (i.e., acoustic input, EEG response
221 elicited by the acoustic input, clapping movement to the acoustic input; Lenc et al.,
222 2021, 2022). Over the past 10 years, this approach has proven to be useful in objectively
223 measuring the input–output transformation performed by the brain, and how this
224 transformation might relate to metre perception (Lenc et al., 2022; Nave et al., 2022;
225 Nozaradan et al., 2017; Stupacher et al., 2016). Here, we predicted that an enhanced
226 representation of the metre will be observed in the post-movement neural and
227 behavioural responses to the rhythmic input (see Table 1). This enhancement was
228 expected to be selective to the metre conveyed by prior movement and magnified for the
229 metre predominant in the participant’s culture.

230 We hypothesised that the amplitude of neural responses at metre frequencies
231 (i.e., three-beat frequencies in the three-beat condition, and four-beat frequencies in the
232 four-beat condition; see Methods) will be enhanced after vs. before the movement
233 session (H_{1a}). This session effect (pre- vs. post-movement) would confirm that
234 short-term multimodal experience of a specific metre as induced by active, intentional
235 movement shapes subsequent internal representation of an auditory rhythm, possibly
236 through perceptual learning (Cannon, 2021; Pearce, 2018). As an alternative, an
237 absence of effect would indicate that (a) the metrical interpretation was already
238 strongly associated with this rhythmic pattern before the body-movement session,
239 possibly driven by a mix of biological and cultural factors (see Kaplan et al., 2022;
240 van der Weij et al., 2017); or (b) the movement session did not provide a sufficient
241 combination of cues (e.g., auditory, vestibular, tactile) to subsequently stabilise a
242 metrical interpretation in such a short period of time.

243 In addition, we hypothesised this session effect on neural responses to be
244 magnified in the four-beat condition (H_{1b}). This interaction effect would indicate that
245 moving to the rhythm is more effective at shaping subsequent neural representation of
246 an auditory rhythm when executed according to a culturally relevant metre (i.e.,
247 four-beat metre). On the other hand, if the session effect is greater in the three-beat
248 condition, this would suggest that, in the culturally familiar condition, the skill level is
249 already relatively high, resulting in a ceiling effect.

250 We also hypothesised that similar effects will be observed at the behavioural
251 level, namely that the amplitude of metre frequencies will be selectively enhanced in the
252 clapping trials (H_{2a}), and that the four-beat movement condition will yield the most
253 powerful effect (H_{2b}). Consistency between brain and behavioural effects would indicate
254 that the observed improvement at clapping the metre in the post-movement session
255 (assumed to be closely related to the way individuals ‘feel’ the metre, due to explicit
256 instructions) is associated with an increased selective representation of the metre
257 frequencies in neural activity. Conversely, observing a significant effect of the movement
258 session in neural but not behavioural responses would suggest that participants may not

259 necessarily use the internal representation of the metre induced by the movement
260 session to guide overt movement beyond the movement session itself.

261

Methods

262 Ethical Clearance

263 The ethics committee of the Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium,
264 approved the present study (ref. 2018-353). Informed consent were obtained from all the
265 participants prior to inclusion in the study. Participants were compensated for their
266 time.

267 Participants

268 Adult volunteers considered eligible to participate in the study were aged
269 between 18 and 45 years, non-musicians and non-dancers, free of sensory (i.e., no
270 auditory impairment or uncorrected visual impairment) and motor dysfunctions (i.e., no
271 upper- and/or lower-limb disorders), and not self-identify as having psychiatric or
272 neurological disorders. In the present study, non-musicians or non-dancers were defined
273 as those meeting at least two out of the three following criteria: (a) not considering
274 themselves as such, (b) not having more than four years of practice, and (c) not having
275 played an instrument/danced in a concert or performance on stage in front of an
276 audience.

277 Participants were included in the African-enculturated group if they
278 self-reported that (a) themselves or both their parents have lived, at least for the first
279 15 years of their lives, in one of the following countries: Mali, Côte d'Ivoire, Togo,
280 Benin, Cameroon, Gabon, Republic of Congo, or Democratic Republic of Congo; and
281 (b) they speak fluently and at least 1h/week one of the idioms (i.e., languages, dialects)
282 from the above-mentioned countries. The screening questionnaire is available for
283 consultation in Supplementary File 1.

284 The sample size for the critical statistical test of each research hypothesis was
285 calculated using R with the 'pwr' and 'WebPower' packages (code is available here:
286 <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>). The EEG and behavioural results of
287 Chemin et al. (2014) were used as a parameter for H_1-H_2 , with one-tailed tests. For H_1 ,

288 the power analysis indicated that eight participants would be required for the session
289 effect ($d = 1.53$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and 20 participants per movement condition would
290 be necessary for the interaction effect between movement condition and session ($f =$
291 0.89 ; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$). For H_2 , six participants would be required for the session
292 effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and 20 participants per movement condition would
293 be necessary for the interaction effect between movement condition and session ($f =$
294 0.89 ; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$). Therefore, a total sample of 40 participants (i.e., 20 per
295 movement condition) was recruited for the present study.

296 The small telescopes approach was used to determine the smallest effect size of
297 interest (SESOI; i.e., the difference that is considered large enough to be meaningful;
298 Simonsohn, 2015). Accordingly, the SESOI was set to the effect size that an earlier study
299 would have had 33% power to detect (Lakens et al., 2018). Here again, the behavioural
300 and EEG results of Chemin et al. (2014) were used as parameters for H_1-H_2 , with
301 one-tailed tests. The SESOI computations were performed using R (code is available as
302 supplementary material here: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>) and
303 the outputs are displayed in Table 1.

304 **Experimental Procedure and Tasks**

305 *Experimental Procedure*

306 Each participant was administered three sessions (~20 min each) on the same
307 day. In the pre- and post-movement sessions, the participant was asked to perform a
308 separate listening and hand-clapping task in a fixed order (see Figure 1, Panel A). Brain
309 activity of the participant was recorded with EEG during the listening task, and
310 behavioural data was collected during the hand-clapping task. In the movement session,
311 half of the participants engaged in the three-beat movement condition while the other
312 half participated in the four-beat movement condition (i.e., between-subjects study
313 design with repeated measures). EEG data was not collected during the movement
314 session. To verify effective behavioural synchronisation in the movement session, an
315 accelerometer was attached to the right foot of the participant and hand-clapping
316 sounds were collected through a microphone. To control for the absence of body

317 movement during the pre- and post-movement sessions, the accelerometer was placed on
318 the participant's head.

319 In the pre- and post-movement sessions, the participant was seated in a
320 comfortable chair, with their head resting against the back of the chair. In these
321 sessions, the participant was instructed to relax, avoid any unnecessary movement, and
322 keep their eyes fixated on a marker displayed on the wall ~1 m in front of them (to
323 minimise large eye movements). During the movement session, the EEG electrode cables
324 were unplugged from the amplifier and attached on the participant's shoulders to free
325 their movements.

326 *Auditory Stimulus*

327 **Description.** The rhythmic pattern used throughout the experiment originates
328 from West and Central Africa, where it often functions as a timeline pattern. It is
329 variously addressed as Bembé or standard bell (Locke, 1982; Toussaint, 2003), among
330 other denominations. In this experiment, this pattern had a duration of 2.4 s and was
331 seamlessly repeated 17 times to form a long sequence, with a total duration of 40.8 s
332 (see Figure 1). Its 'x.x.xx.x.x.x' structure is based on a 12-interval grid ($200 \text{ ms} \times 12 =$
333 2.4 s), following a specific arrangement of seven 200-ms sound events (depicted by the
334 'x', and made of a 200-Hz pure tones with 10-ms rise and 50-ms fall linear ramps) and
335 five 200-ms silent intervals (depicted by the ':').

336 This rhythmic stimulus is particularly relevant to the present study for several
337 reasons. Firstly, the rhythmic pattern is culturally valid due to its wide use across
338 musical traditions in Central and West Africa (Locke, 1982; Temperley, 2000). Yet, the
339 pattern can be presented in a decontextualized fashion for the purposes of the current
340 study (e.g., by using pure tones instead of a clave sound that typically delivers the
341 pattern in stylistically valid contexts), thus minimising the interference caused by
342 non-rhythmic contextual cues in participants familiar with musical repertoires
343 containing this pattern. Unlike stimuli used in the majority of prior studies (e.g.,
344 Chemin et al., 2014; Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007), the groups of tones making
345 up the pattern are arranged in a way that a tone does not systematically coincide with

346 each beat, thus reducing the likelihood of acoustic or low-level sensory confounds (see
347 Lenc et al., 2021; Nozaradan et al., 2016). This holds for beat pulses that are used in
348 both the three- or four-beat metre condition. Moreover, an overlap between the internal
349 beat and the arrangement of tones in the rhythm cannot be achieved by simply shifting
350 the phase (or alignment) of the beat with respect to the stimulus.

351 In the movement session, a metronome-like acoustic pulse was added to the
352 auditory stimulus and served as a cue to the beat from the targeted metre. This pulse
353 consisted of a low-pitched drum sound presented isochronously with an inter-onset
354 interval of 800 ms in the three-beat metre condition and 600 ms in the four-beat metre
355 condition, thus yielding three or four drum cues per repetition of the 2.4-s rhythmic
356 pattern, respectively. In the three-beat metre condition, the pulses were aligned with
357 the first, fifth, and ninth time point on the grid used to generate the rhythmic pattern.
358 In the four-beat metre condition, the pulses occurred at the first, fourth, seventh, and
359 tenth grid point (see Figure 2, Panel B). The drum sound coinciding with the first grid
360 point was accented (sound intensity increased by 2.5 dB) to emphasise the onset of each
361 repetition of the pattern. Three additional repetitions of the rhythmic pattern without
362 the overlaid pulse were appended at the end of the auditory stimulus (40.8 s of auditory
363 stimulation with the overlaid pulse and 7.2 without, for a total trial duration of 48 s; see
364 Figure 1, Panel A). The three auditory stimuli were generated using MATLAB (version
365 R2022a; MathWorks, Portola Valley, CA).

366 **Sound Analysis.** To control for acoustic or low-level sensory confounds that
367 may bias the results, it is critical to measure how prominent the periodicities
368 corresponding to the three- and four-beat metrical interpretations are in the rhythmic
369 stimulus (Lenc et al., 2021). To this end, the amplitude envelope of the 40.8-s auditory
370 sequence was extracted using a Hilbert transform and converted into the frequency
371 domain using a fast Fourier transform (Lenc et al., 2021; Nozaradan et al., 2017),
372 allowing to estimate the prominence of periodicities in the continuous modulation of the
373 stimulus acoustic features. The obtained envelope spectrum contains 12 distinct
374 amplitude peaks (see Figure 2, Panel A), corresponding to the repetition frequency of

375 the whole rhythmic pattern (i.e., $1/2.4 \text{ s} = 0.42 \text{ Hz}$) and its harmonics up to the
 376 shortest intervals between single events (i.e., $1/0.2 \text{ s} = 5 \text{ Hz}$; Lenc et al., 2021). To
 377 match analysis of the EEG signals (see below ‘EEG Data’ subsection), the first and last
 378 frequency (i.e., 0.42 and 5 Hz, respectively) of the spectrum were discarded from further
 379 computation.

380 To assess the relative prominence of frequencies considered as related to the
 381 metre vs. the other, metre-unrelated frequencies, the magnitudes of responses at the 10
 382 frequencies of interest were then converted into z scores following Equation 1 (see
 383 Figure 2, Panel B; Lenc et al., 2018):

$$z_i = \frac{A_i - \bar{A}_{\text{all}}}{s_{\text{all}}} \quad (1)$$

384 where i is a given frequency of interest, A is the amplitude, and s is the standard
 385 deviation. Finally, the obtained z scores were averaged across metre frequencies (i.e.,
 386 the frequency corresponding to the metre periodicity and harmonics: 1.25 and 3.75 Hz
 387 in the three-beat condition, and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33 and 4.17 Hz in the four-beat condition).
 388 Note that the sixth frequency (i.e., 2.5 Hz) was dismissed as it is found in both metrical
 389 interpretations. As displayed in Figure 2 (Panel C), the stimulus contains a virtually
 390 equivalent low acoustic energy (z scores < 0) at either of the two metre periodicities
 391 considered here, when compared to the remaining frequencies constituting the envelope
 392 spectrum of the rhythm.

393 *Tasks Description*

394 The auditory stimuli were presented binaurally via insert earphones (ER-2,
 395 Etymotic Research; air-conducted sound from the level of the participant’s clavicle to
 396 decrease magnetic interferences), connected to a Fireface UC audio interface (RME
 397 Audio, Haimhausen, Germany; sampling frequency = 44100 Hz; sound volume = 73 dB
 398 sound pressure level [SPL]). In the listening task (i.e., during which EEG signals were
 399 collected), the auditory stimulus was played to the participant while they were required
 400 to perform an orthogonal task to encourage attentive listening. More precisely, the
 401 participant was instructed to detect speed reduction in the temporal structure of the
 402 auditory stimulus and report their response at the end of each trial (i.e., to avoid

403 speech-related artifacts during the EEG recording). This tempo change was applied to
404 the tenth repetition of the rhythmic pattern within the trial by increasing the spacing of
405 the underlying time grid by 7.5%, lengthening the duration of that repetition from 2.4 s
406 to 2.58 s. There was a total of two trials per session containing this deviant period (with
407 those trials being randomly positioned across participants), and these trials were
408 discarded from further analyses. In the hand-clapping task (i.e., which directly followed
409 the listening task in both the pre- and post-movement sessions; see Figure 1, Panel A),
410 the participant was instructed to clap along with the beat they perceived in the auditory
411 stimulus ('Clap your hands as you would clap in sync with the music at a concert').

412 During the movement session (i.e., without EEG recordings), the participant was
413 asked to step on-the-spot and clap with their hands (i.e., whole-body movements) in
414 synchrony with the beat according to a specific metrical interpretation of the rhythmic
415 pattern, as indicated with the drum cue. In the last three repetitions of the rhythmic
416 pattern, the pulse prompter was stopped, and the participant thus needed to continue
417 synchronising to the same metrical interpretation without the pulse prompter (i.e.,
418 synchronisation-continuation task; see e.g., Repp, 2001; Rose et al., 2021). Detailed
419 task instructions can be found in Supplementary File 1.

420 *Experimental Design*

421 The experiment used a fixed block-design procedure (see Figure 1), with each
422 trial lasting 40.8 s in the pre- and post-movement sessions and 48 s in the movement
423 session. The pre- and post-movement sessions were composed of 18 trials for the
424 listening task (including two randomly placed trials containing the deviant period to be
425 detected for the orthogonal task), followed by five trials for the hand-clapping task. The
426 movement session consisted of 18 trials. To assess the participant's familiarity with the
427 stimulus, they were asked whether they recognised the rhythmic pattern during the
428 debriefing session at the end of the experiment. The total duration of the experimental
429 procedure was ~1 hr.

430 **Data Acquisition and Pre-Processing Analyses**

431 Data acquisition was performed using an ActiveTwo system (BioSemi,
432 Amsterdam, Netherlands) and facilitated by the ActiView software (version 8.13). All
433 the pre-processing analyses were performed using MATLAB (version R2022a). Data
434 collection and analysis were not performed blind to the conditions of the study. To
435 avoid a confounding effect of the experimenter, the first and second authors of this
436 article (who each led one of the two Stage 2 articles) each collected data from half of
437 the participants in the two experimental groups. Pilot tests were run ($n = 1$ in the
438 three- and four-beat movement condition) to confirm that the experimental protocol
439 and data collection were logistically feasible and that planned analyses allowed us to
440 test the research hypotheses (see Supplementary File 2).

441 **EEG Data**

442 The EEG data were recorded with 64 Ag/AgCl pin-type active electrodes placed
443 on the participant's scalp according to the International 10–20 system guidelines for
444 standard electrode placement (Jasper, 1958). In addition, two flat-type active electrodes
445 were located over the left and right mastoids. Signals were referenced to the
446 common-mode sense electrode and digitised at a 1024-Hz sampling rate. Electrodes
447 offset relative to the common mode sense (CMS) and driven leg (DRL) electrode loop
448 was kept below ± 50 mV.

449 The EEG data were pre-processed using Letswave6 built-in functions
450 (<https://github.com/NOCIONS/letswave6>) and custom MATLAB scripts. The raw
451 data were band-pass filtered using a 0.1–64 Hz Butterworth filter (4th order) in order to
452 eliminate very slow drifts and high frequencies irrelevant to the present study (while
453 also allowing further down sampling of the data if necessary). The filtered signals were
454 segmented from -5 s to +45.8 s (i.e., 5-s buffer at the beginning and end) with respect
455 to the onset to each trial. Based on visual inspection, channels containing excessive
456 artefacts or noise were linearly interpolated using the three closest channels (based on
457 Cartesian coordinates). Note that a channel that was interpolated in one EEG session
458 was also interpolated in the other EEG session of the same participant to prevent

459 confounds. 2.5% of the channels were interpolated on this basis. In addition, trials
460 showing excessive artefacts were rejected. Across all participants, seven trials were
461 rejected on this basis. The full data set of a participant were removed prior to further
462 analyses if $> 15\%$ of the channels were interpolated and/or > 3 trials per session were
463 rejected (see Figure 3). Nine participants were removed on this basis. Any excluded
464 participant were replaced to ensure that $n = 20$ per group.

465 Independent component analysis was applied to concatenated segments (from 0
466 to 40.8 s relative to the trial onset) of all trials and sessions, down-sampled to 256 Hz
467 with the purpose of reducing computation time. For each participant, the independent
468 components related to eye blinks were identified through visual inspection of the first 10
469 independent components' waveform and topography, and removed from the EEG
470 signals. Data were then re-referenced to the mean of the two mastoids electrodes,
471 averaged across trials, and epoched from 2.4 to 40.8 s with respect to trial onset (i.e.,
472 removal of the 5-s buffer and first pattern repetition), resulting in epochs of 38.4 s.

473 For each electrode, the averaged waveforms were transformed into the frequency
474 domain using fast Fourier transform, yielding a spectrum of signal amplitudes (in μV)
475 ranging from 0 to 512 Hz, with a frequency resolution of 0.026 Hz (i.e., $1/38.4$ s). To
476 obtain valid estimates of the EEG responses, the contribution of residual background
477 noise was minimised by subtracting, at each frequency bin, the mean amplitude of the
478 four neighbouring bins (2nd to 5th on both sides; see Bouvet et al., 2020; Lenc et al.,
479 2022). The frequencies were then averaged across a cluster of nine fronto-central
480 electrodes (i.e., F1, Fz, F2, FC1, FCz, FC2, C1, Cz, C2), which have been found to
481 exhibit strong frequency-tagged responses to rhythmic stimuli in previous studies (see
482 Nozaradan et al., 2012, 2016, 2017).

483 For each participant and session, the amplitude was measured at frequencies of
484 interest that were defined based on the temporal structure of the rhythmic pattern.
485 Specifically, these frequencies of interest corresponded to the pattern repetition rate and
486 harmonics ($1/2.4$ s = 0.42 Hz), up to the frequency equivalent to the shortest interval
487 between the onset of individual sounds composing the rhythmic pattern ($1/0.2$ s = 5

488 Hz). This frequency range of interest was determined based on previous studies (see
489 e.g., Lenc et al., 2020, 2022), showing that surface EEG responses to rhythmic acoustic
490 patterns – similar to the one that was used in the present study – mainly project onto
491 this frequency range. From the resulting set of 12 harmonic frequencies, the first
492 frequency (i.e., 0.42 Hz) was discarded prior to further analyses, because located in a
493 frequency range that is typically strongly affected by the characteristic $1/f$ background
494 noise observed in EEG spectra (i.e., prone to unreliable measurement; Cirelli et al.,
495 2016; Lenc et al., 2022). The last harmonic frequency (i.e., 5 Hz) was also dismissed, as
496 its amplitude is likely driven by the shape of the individual 200-ms sounds composing
497 the rhythmic pattern (see Figure 2, left part, for depiction of these frequencies as
498 identified in the modulation spectrum of the stimulus).

499 From this set, the purpose of the study was to assess the relative prominence of
500 frequencies considered as related to the metre periodicity vs. the other, metre-unrelated
501 frequencies (Lenc et al., 2018). To this aim, the amplitude at each of these 10
502 frequencies of interest were converted into z scores (see Equation 1). Finally, the
503 obtained z scores were averaged across metre frequencies (i.e., 1.25 and 3.75 Hz in the
504 three-beat condition [i.e., $\bar{z}_{\text{EEG},3\text{-beat}}$], and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33, and 4.17 Hz in the four-beat
505 condition [i.e., $\bar{z}_{\text{EEG},4\text{-beat}}$]). Along the lines of the sound analysis, the sixth frequency
506 (i.e., 2.5 Hz) was dismissed as it is found in both metrical interpretations.

507 *Behavioural Data*

508 **Hand Clapping.** Hand clapping was collected using a microphone (ATR20;
509 Audio-Technica, Machida, Japan) and digitised through the Fireface UC audio interface
510 (sampling rate = 44100 Hz).

511 ***Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions.*** The continuous sound signal recorded
512 during the pre- and post-movement sessions was segmented into epochs lasting 38.4 s
513 (from 2.4 to 40.8 s with respect to trial onset). Note that the first pattern repetition of
514 each epoch was removed to match epoching of the EEG data. Claps were detected in
515 the sound signal using the ‘findpeaks’ function and IRIs were computed for each trial.

516 The recorded clapping signal was also analysed in the frequency domain,
517 similarly to the EEG and sound signals. The continuous sound signal was averaged
518 across trials. The amplitude envelope of this mean signal was extracted using a Hilbert
519 transform and transformed in the frequency domain using a fast Fourier transform
520 (frequency resolution = 0.026 Hz; i.e., 1/38.4 s trial duration). To match with the
521 analysis procedure applied on EEG data, noise subtraction was also applied to the
522 obtained spectra. Finally, $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ was computed following the same method described
523 for the EEG data (see Equation 1).

524 ***Movement Session.*** The continuous audio signal of clapping obtained from
525 participants instructed to synchronise clapping to the drum cue was segmented into
526 epochs lasting 45.6 s (from 2.4 to 48 s with respect to trial onset). Claps were detected
527 using a find peaks function applied onto the envelope extracted from the recording
528 signals. The signed asynchrony was computed as the difference between each clap and
529 its associated pulse. Signed asynchrony is negative when the clap is preceding the
530 targeted drum cue, and positive when the clap is following the targeted drum cue. The
531 mean signed asynchrony within a trial was calculated as a measure of synchrony with
532 the pulse prompter.

533 ***Stepping.*** Stepping performed during the movement session was recorded using
534 an accelerometer placed on the participant's right foot (ADXL335; Adafruit, New York,
535 USA), and digitised through the BioSemi analog input box (sampling rate = 1024 Hz).
536 As for the hand-clapping data, the obtained continuous acceleration signal was
537 segmented into epochs lasting 45.6 s (from 2.4 to 48 s with respect to trial onset), steps
538 were detected using a find peaks function (the detected peaks corresponded to the
539 initial-contact phase; Buckley et al., 2019; Sant'Anna & Wickström, 2010), and
540 inter-response intervals (IRIs) were computed. The IRIs time series were then divided
541 by two, to account for data recorded from one foot only. The asynchrony indices were
542 computed following the same method described for the hand-clapping data.

543 *Control Measures*

544 **Effectiveness of Auditory Stimulation.** A prerequisite to our hypotheses
 545 was the ability to capture the neural responses to an auditory rhythm with EEG. As a
 546 control measure for this assumption, the frequencies of interest as determined above
 547 (i.e., 0.83, 1.25, 1.67, 2.08, 2.5, 2.92, 3.33, 3.75, and 4.17 Hz) should significantly stand
 548 out relatively to background noise in the EEG signal (see Lenc et al., 2018; Nozaradan,
 549 2014; Nozaradan et al., 2018). Thus, as a positive control, an index of standardised
 550 signal-to-noise ratio ($z_{\text{SNR,EEG}}$) of the frequencies of interest was computed from the
 551 raw, non-subtracted amplitude spectrum of EEG data averaged across the
 552 fronto-central channels (see Figure 3; Bottari et al., 2020; Vettori et al., 2020).

553 In each participant’s spectrum (without noise subtraction), the amplitude at
 554 each frequency of interest along with its 20 neighbouring bins (10 on both sides,
 555 representative of local background noise) was selected, thus resulting in 10 segments of
 556 21 values. These segments were then averaged, yielding an averaged segment where the
 557 11th value thus corresponded to the averaged amplitude across the 10 frequencies of
 558 interest. This averaged segment was then standardised into a z score with Equation 2:

$$z_{\text{SNR,EEG}} = \frac{A_{11\text{th}} - \bar{A}_{\text{background}}}{s_{\text{background}}} \quad (2)$$

559 where A is the amplitude and s is the standard deviation. This index served as a
 560 measure of the overall prominence of EEG responses to the auditory stimulus over
 561 background noise.

562 **Absence of Rhythmic Head Movements During EEG Recordings.** A
 563 possible confounding factor of the present study was that the selective enhancement of
 564 EEG responses at metre-related frequencies was not due to neural responses per se but
 565 to unintentional rhythmic movements of the participant’s head while they listened to
 566 the rhythmic stimulus. To control for this potential artefact, head movements were
 567 recorded using the accelerometer during the listening trials of the pre- and post-training
 568 sessions. The $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ of metre-related frequencies (i.e., 1.25, 2.50, and 3.75 Hz) was
 569 computed following the same method described for the EEG data (see Equation 2). This
 570 index served as an indicator of head synchronisation with metre-related frequencies.

571 **Statistical Analyses**572 ***Data Eligible for Analysis***

573 **Outcome-Neutral Criteria.** As described in more details above, only data
574 coming from participants with $\leq 15\%$ of interpolated channels and ≤ 3 rejected trials
575 per session were analysed (see Figure 3).

576 **Positive Control.** No participant's data set was excluded from the analyses
577 because $z_{\text{SNR,EEG}} < 1.96$ (i.e., $\alpha > .02$), indicating that neural responses were elicited by
578 the rhythmic stimulus in every participant.

579 ***Performed Analyses***

580 R was used for the statistical analyses, with alpha set at $p < .020$ (i.e., in accord
581 with the strictest available stipulations from the list of *PCI RR*-friendly journals). For
582 each statistical comparison, the effect sizes (i.e., η_p^2 , Cohen's d) are reported as a
583 quantification of the experimental-effect magnitude and interpreted in accord with
584 Cohen's (1988) guidelines. For effect sizes that are presented as Cohen's d , $d < 0.5$ was
585 considered as small, $d \geq 0.5$ as medium, and $d \geq 0.8$ as large. Where effect sizes are
586 presented as η_p^2 , $\eta_p^2 \geq .01$ was considered as small, $\eta_p^2 \geq .06$ as medium, and $\eta_p^2 \geq .14$ as
587 large. To test the robustness of our statistical outcomes (for the importance of
588 conducting multiverse analyses, see Wagenmakers et al., 2023), linear mixed models
589 were also used to test each hypothesis (with the 'lme4' and 'emmeans' packages), and
590 the results are reported in Supplementary File 3.

591 To examine H_1-H_2 , a two-way mixed-model analysis of variance (ANOVA;
592 Session [pre vs. post movement] \times Movement Condition [three- vs. four-beat metre])
593 was applied on the two dependent variables, \bar{z}_{EEG} and $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ (see Table 1). To
594 demonstrate that periodic head movements did not contribute significantly to the
595 effects found in the EEG (if any), an identical ANOVA model was applied on $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$.

596 Normality of residuals was checked using the R 'performance' package (Lüdtke
597 et al., 2021); if violated, the data were normalised using a transformation that will be
598 contingent on data distribution curves. Where Mauchly's tests indicated violations of
599 the sphericity assumption, Greenhouse–Geisser corrections were applied. Independent

600 and pairwise post hoc t tests with Bonferroni adjustments for multiple comparisons
601 were used where necessary to identify where differences lie.

602

Results

603 Demographic information about our sample along with data about familiarity
604 with the rhythmic pattern are available in Figure 4 (Panel A and Panel B, respectively).

605 Data Screening and Diagnostics

606 Data screening indicated that there were two univariate outliers, associated with
607 \bar{z}_{EEG} ($k = 1$), and $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ ($k = 1$) measures. These were adjusted using a winsorization
608 procedure (Sullivan et al., 2021) until they came within the range $-3.29 < z < +3.29$ (see
609 Tabachnick & Fidell, 2018). Normality tests indicated that $z_{\text{SNR,head}}$ exhibited instances
610 of non-normality ($p < .001$). A square root transformation was applied to remedy this.

611 EEG Data

612 The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) < 0.01$, p
613 $= .969$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 0.25$, $p = .617$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$ (see
614 Figure 5). The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1,$
615 $38) = 0.36$, $p = .554$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that amplitude of neural
616 responses at metre frequencies primed during the preceding body-movement session
617 were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session.

618 The original selection of metre-related and metre-unrelated frequencies was
619 determined from both the stimulus spectrum and plausible beat periodicities
620 compatible with each metrical interpretation. As a robustness check, an alternative
621 selection of metre-related frequencies solely based on the rate of the learning cue during
622 the body-movement session was also considered. These additional analyses are reported
623 in Supplementary File 4. The neural results remained unchanged.

624 Additionally, due to the disparity in the number of metre-related frequencies
625 between the two metrical interpretations, the value of \bar{z} is constrained to a range of -1.16
626 to $+1.16$ in the four-beat metre condition, whereas in the three-beat metre condition, it
627 can vary between -1.90 and $+1.90$. Additional analyses to address this compression
628 effect, both for the registered analyses and the selection of metre-related frequencies

629 based on the learning cues (see Supplementary File 4), are detailed in Supplementary
630 File 5. However, the results remained unchanged after controlling for this effect.

631 **Behavioural Data**

632 *Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions*

633 The RM ANOVA showed a significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) = 13.43$, p
634 $< .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .26$, with larger $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ after ($M = 0.49$, $SD = 0.67$) when compared to
635 before the movement ($M = 0.13$, $SD = 0.71$, $d = 0.58$; see Figure XX). Note that the
636 effect size is larger than the required SESOI (see Table 1), which indicated that the
637 effect is sufficiently strong to be considered meaningful. The main effect of movement
638 condition was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.57$, $p = .455$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. The Session \times
639 Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.45$, $p = .505$, η_p^2
640 $= .01$. Overall, the results indicated that the participants clapped periodically following
641 the metre as primed in the preceding body-movement session to a greater extent after
642 vs. before the movement session.

643 With the alternative selection of metre-related frequencies reflecting the rate of
644 the learning cue (see Supplementary File 4), the main effect of session was no longer
645 significant with the stringent p value adopted in the study ($.050 > p > .020$). However,
646 a main effect of condition emerged, corroborating the hypothesis of a stronger
647 interpretation of the rhythm according to its associated cultural convention (i.e., higher
648 z scores in the four-beat condition).

649 Additional analyses to address the above-mentioned compression effect are
650 detailed in Supplementary File 4. Overall, these analyses corroborated the results, but
651 also showed an additional main effect of condition in favour of the culturally typical and
652 familiar four-beat metre.

653 *Learning Accuracy*

654 The ANOVA performed on the hand clapping signed asynchrony did not show a
655 significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 38) = 2.94$, $p < .094$, $\eta_p^2 = .07$. An
656 independent TOST procedure (raw equivalence bound = 0.01; based on Rose et al.,
657 2021) showed that both t tests were significant, $t_{\text{upper}}(38) = -2.17$, $p = .018$, $t_{\text{lower}}(38) =$

658 2.17, $p = .018$. Moreover, the ANOVA performed on the stepping signed asynchrony did
659 not show a significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 35) = 0.27$, $p < .606$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. An
660 independent TOST procedure (raw equivalence bound = 0.01) showed that both t tests
661 were nonsignificant, $t_{\text{upper}}(38) = -0.74$, $p = .231$, $t_{\text{lower}}(38) = 0.74$, $p = .231$. Overall,
662 these results indicated that both the clapping and stepping accuracy during the
663 body-movement session were not significantly different between the two conditions.
664 Equivalence was established only for the clapping data, confirming that clapping
665 accuracy was *similar* across the two metre conditions.

666 **Head Movements**

667 Due to non-normality of residuals, the data were transformed using square root
668 transformation. The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38)$
669 $= 1.12$, $p = .296$, $\eta_p^2 = .03$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = .04$, $p = .836$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$.
670 The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) =$
671 0.49 , $p = .488$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. Overall, the results indicated that periodic head movements
672 (a) were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session and (b) were not different
673 between experimental conditions.

674 **Supplementary Analyses**

675 ***Hand Clapping***

676 To assess clapping stability during the learning session, the vector strength of
677 the asynchrony between claps and the drum cues marking the beat in each movement
678 condition was computed (Fisher, 1995; Large et al., 2015). In circular statistics, vector
679 strength values range from 0 (i.e., no synchronisation) to 1 (i.e., maximum
680 synchronisation). Following a rank-based inverse normal transformation to ensure
681 normality of residuals, the one-way independent measures ANOVA did not yield a
682 significant main effect of condition, $F(1,38) = 4.73$, $p = .036$, $\eta_p^2 = .11$.

683 ***Stepping***

684 The vector strength was also calculated for asynchronies between steps and the
685 drum cues, for all participants except two, for whom step onsets could not be extracted

686 reliably due to noisy signals. The data was then transformed using a rank-based inverse
687 normal approach to ensure normality of the residuals, and the one-way independent
688 measures ANOVA showed no main effect of condition, $F(1,36) = 1.89$, $p = .178$, $\eta_p^2 =$
689 $.05$.

690

Discussion

691 The purpose of this registered report was to provide original insights into
692 auditory rhythm perception in humans, by investigating how it is continuously shaped
693 through the interplay with motor engagement and multisensory integration.
694 Behavioural results showed a propensity to clap the metre primed in the preceding
695 body-movement session to a greater extent after vs. before the movement session,
696 showing that short-term motor engagement can shape rhythmic behaviour beyond
697 cultural experience. In contrast, EEG data did not show corresponding enhancement of
698 neural responses, suggesting that a single brief movement session may not be sufficient
699 to stabilise a metre representation that can be reactivated automatically (i.e., without
700 an explicit, related task).

701 Imprints of Motor Engagement onto Rhythm Processing

702 In line with the hypotheses, the amplitude of metre-related frequencies was
703 selectively enhanced in clapping trials performed after, relative to before, the brief body
704 movement session. This corroborates previous research demonstrating an effect of
705 priming on subsequent rhythm processing, both in infants (Flaten et al., 2022;
706 Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005) and adults (Chemin et al., 2014; Phillips-Silver &
707 Trainor, 2007; Su & Pöppel, 2012). The finding also extends current knowledge by
708 showing that this short-term learning effect can arise in the context of weakly periodic
709 rhythms – where there is no prominent acoustic cue to the beat periodicity in the
710 stimulus. Together, the results thus suggest that short-term motor engagement may
711 facilitate the learning of an internal representation of rhythm, or rhythm–metre
712 association, that goes beyond enhancement of already salient acoustic cues.

713 With regard to underlying mechanisms, body movements may act as a form of
714 rhythmic priming. Specifically, this priming would facilitate perceptual selection by

715 directing attention towards behaviourally relevant auditory information (Large &
716 Snyder, 2009; Large et al., 2023; Morillon et al., 2015). The resulting temporal template
717 may subsequently be recruited to guide overt movement (see Morillon & Baillet, 2017).
718 A related possibility is that metre perception is tuned through the multisensory
719 experience provided by moving the body along with external rhythmic sensory inputs,
720 yielding integration of proprioceptive, visual, auditory and tactile rhythmic inputs. Such
721 multisensory rhythms produced by body movement would thus strengthen metre
722 through self-entrainment processes (Cannon, 2025). This view is also in line with the
723 framework of embodied cognition, whereby cognitive representations dynamically
724 interact with motor systems (Witek, 2023). More specifically, movement performed
725 during entrainment to a beat is thought to inform a predictive model that in turn
726 structures perceptual processing. The richness of the multisensory experience is likely to
727 enhance the precision of this predictive model (Vuust et al., 2022). In the present study,
728 participants engaged in whole-body movement to the rhythm, specifically clapping and
729 stepping. Such movement provides robust multisensory input, which may account for
730 why even a brief movement session – relative to longer-term cultural experience – was
731 sufficient to elicit effects with a rhythm lacking prominent cues to the metre in its
732 acoustic structure.

733 **Interplay of Short-Term Motor Engagement and Longer-Term Cultural** 734 **Experience**

735 It is worth noting the cultural congruence between the stimulus and the
736 participant sample in the present study (Polak, 2026). That is, the rhythm was
737 purposely selected to match the participants' enculturation. In doing so, the study aims
738 to address a critical gap in psychology and neuroscience, by focusing on a population
739 that is still largely underrepresented in most research (see Jacoby et al., 2024;
740 Jakubowski et al., 2025; Kwon et al., 2021; Moriguchi, 2022). It also allowed to test the
741 interaction between short-term motor engagement and longer-term cultural experience
742 in rhythm processing. More specifically, repeated rhythmic patterns (often referred to as
743 *ostinatos*, *timeline*, or *bell/clave patterns*) are known to play a key role in providing

744 temporal reference in African(-derived) musical traditions (Agawu, 2006; Benadon,
745 2020; Polak, 2026; Poole, 2018). The use of such repeated rhythmic patterns in the
746 stimulus of the present study may therefore have elicited learned associations with
747 familiar musical repertoires, assumed to result from long-term learning process over the
748 course of enculturation, thereby activating an existing internal representation or
749 temporal template. This interpretation may account for the relative greater propensity
750 to clap according to the culturally congruent four-beat metre in the baseline session. It
751 is also corroborated by participants' debriefing statements to the question "Did the
752 rhythm remind you of something?", which explicitly associated the rhythm with cultural
753 practices (e.g., "Same rhythm as certain pieces of our traditional African music",
754 "[Rhythm of] village festivals, concerts or family celebrations", "To the beat of the
755 tam-tam in traditional African songs", "It's similar to the rhythm I often do with family
756 or friends"). This hypothesis will also be examined through cross-cultural comparisons
757 between African- and European-enculturated participants in the second Stage 2 article
758 resulting from this programmatic registered report (see Coulon et al., 2026).

759 In the current study, motor engagement affected subsequent rhythm processing
760 to a comparable degree for both three- and four-beat metre conditions – thus
761 irrespective of cultural conventions. These results suggest that African-enculturated
762 participants' meter perception is flexible (Benadon, 2020; Cameron et al., 2015; Locke,
763 2011; Temperley, 2000), especially once the temporal structure of the rhythmic pattern
764 has been grasped. These results could also be considered in relation to the relatively
765 decontextualised presentation of the stimulus used in the present study. Specifically, the
766 stimulus lacked the timbre of the instrument that typically conveys the rhythm, and
767 was isolated from other music ensemble parts and related expressive modes (e.g.,
768 dancing) in which this rhythm usually occurs.

769 Previous research has shown that Western-enculturated individuals tend to
770 organise fast musical events in groups of two or four (Bergeson & Trehub, 2006; Drake
771 & Palmer, 1993; Fraise, 1982; Møller et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2013). By contrast, the
772 present study with African-enculturated participants provided no evidence of such a

773 binary bias evident in the clapping time series. A plausible explanation is that, rather
774 than grouping the fast stream of events underlying the rhythm sequence in a binary
775 manner, African-enculturated participants relied on their cultural experience to process
776 the embedded rhythmic pattern as a whole. This holistic processing would allow the
777 rhythmic pattern to be subdivided in a binary manner, resulting in two or four
778 perceived beats per pattern repetition. Future research could disentangle these
779 possibilities by investigating how the degradation of pattern repetition across conditions
780 (for an implementation, see e.g., Coulon et al., 2025) impacts beat processing in
781 participants who are familiar with musical practices in which pattern repetition plays a
782 central role (as is the case for the cultural group tested in the present study, with the
783 so-called timelines are used as a rhythmic backbone; Agawu, 2006; Kubik, 2010; Locke,
784 1982); and by comparing these effects with those observed in European-enculturated
785 participants, as examined in previous investigation of the binary bias (Bååth, 2015;
786 Møller et al., 2021).

787 **Inconsistency Between Brain and Behavioural Responses**

788 While a brief movement session led to subsequent enhancement of metre-related
789 frequencies in the clapping responses, this was not the case for neural activity captured
790 during the post-movement listening task. In other words, the current results show that
791 a brief 20-minute movement session was not sufficient to automatically foster the neural
792 representation of learned metrical interpretations after movement cessation.

793 This may be due to the complexity of the rhythmic pattern used, which lacked
794 salient acoustic periodicities corresponding to plausible metrical interpretations (see
795 Figure 2). Such rhythms may necessitate a massive transformation of the sensory input
796 – including engagement of higher-order cortical areas – in order to be periodised into a
797 metre-related internal representation (see Lenc et al., 2021). Therefore, compared to
798 rhythms containing prominent metre-related periodicities (see e.g., Chemin et al., 2014;
799 Phillips-Silver & Trainor, 2005, 2007), rhythms with weak periodic cues may require
800 more time and repeated presentation to be robustly associated with a periodic internal
801 template.

802 Nonetheless, the current results show that, when required to move to such a
803 complex yet culturally familiar rhythm, participants were able to activate the learned
804 rhythm–metre association to guide intentional overt movements (Brower, 1993). One
805 plausible mechanism is that participants “re-enacted” the target interval duration
806 between successive movements – as in a synchronisation-continuation task – and
807 mapped this interval onto the rhythm. This strategy would allow them to maintain an
808 approximate alignment between the auditory stimuli and motor responses without
809 relying on an explicit internal representation of the metre. Such an outcome may
810 further reflect how participants approached the body-movement session. Specifically, the
811 intended process was to integrate the acoustic metre prompt with the metre as
812 embodied in the movement, and to map both onto the rhythmic pattern during motor
813 training. By contrast, participants may have instead directed their attentional resources
814 primarily on the drum sound cue in order to comply with the task and synchronise their
815 movements. This focus may have occurred at the expense of processing the broader
816 configuration of rhythm and metre as a cohesive whole (Keller & Burnham, 2005).

817 However, the interpretation that participants reproduced the target interval
818 purely from memory while ignoring the auditory input is not supported by the data. In
819 the absence of ongoing coupling between movement and sound, progressive
820 desynchronisation would be expected due to error accumulation, resulting in spectral
821 leakage and the absence of narrow peaks at the frequencies of interest. Instead, the fact
822 that clear peaks were observed in the tapping spectra points towards sustained
823 integration between the auditory input and the internal representation of metre. Hence,
824 memory for the absolute target interval alone cannot fully explain the results (although
825 it may have contributed, especially given that tempo was kept constant across sessions).

826 In any case, the cultural relevance of the rhythm, as confirmed by participants’
827 ratings on the familiarity questionnaire (see Figure 4, Panel B), did facilitate the brain
828 transformation that supports the mapping between rhythm and metre, but only when
829 the task involved active motor engagement. In this respect, it is important to emphasise
830 that the auditory stimulus used in the present study was a decontextualised version of a

831 rhythmic pattern found in African and African-derived musical traditions.
832 Consequently, contextual cues usually associated with the rhythm could not be
833 leveraged to scaffold a learned rhythm–meter association, even among participants
834 familiar with repertoires containing this pattern. This may have interfered with the
835 spontaneous activation of culturally grounded metrical frameworks, thereby limiting the
836 extent to which familiarity could exert a facilitating effect without the multimodal
837 stimulation and additional processes present during the clapping task (for discussion of
838 context effects in cross-cultural rhythm perception research, see Polak et al., 2026). In
839 addition, although participants were African-enculturated, they had all resided in
840 Belgium for an average of five years (range = 1– 15 years). These findings highlight the
841 complexity of characterising enculturation: it should not be conceived as a static
842 attribute determined solely by early exposure, but rather as a dynamic process of
843 ongoing cultural experience shaped by the context of learning and practice, and the
844 coexistence of multiple environments (Kim & Alamilla, 2017; Polak et al., 2026).
845 Accordingly, extended experience with a different cultural environment may attenuate
846 or reshape the impact of early musical experience on rhythm and metre processing.

847 **Conclusions**

848 The present findings demonstrate that even a brief engagement in body
849 movement can selectively enhance behavioural alignment with a rhythm, highlighting
850 the role of motor engagement in scaffolding internal rhythm representations, beyond
851 cultural experience. However, this enhancement does not automatically translate into
852 increased neural responses at metre-related frequencies, at least for context-free and
853 weakly periodic rhythms. The dissociation between behavioural and neural indices
854 suggests that associating internal representation of meter to complex rhythms relies on
855 multi-level processing, and that such association is not achieved through a single, brief
856 movement session. Taken together, these findings provide empirical support for the
857 interactive contributions of motor engagement, multisensory integration, and cultural
858 experience in shaping rhythm perception. The obtained results thus offer novel insights

859 into the mechanisms by which the brain flexibly maps rhythmic inputs onto holistic
860 internal templates.

861

Open Practices

Data Availability

863 Pilot data, along with all anonymised raw and processed data supporting the
864 reported analyses, are available on a public Zenodo repository
865 (<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10221480>).

Code Availability

867 The scripts used to conduct the power analysis and all scripts supporting the
868 reported analyses are available on a public GitHub repository
869 (https://github.com/segoleneguerin/meter_learning_motor).

870

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884

Competing Interests

885 The authors have no competing financial interests to declare.

886

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Table 1*Estimated Required Sample and Effect Sizes*

Question	Hypothesis	Analysis plan	Sampling plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given to different outcomes
The amplitude of neural responses at metre-related frequencies will be enhanced after vs. before the movement session, and this effect will be magnified in the four-beat metre condition.	\bar{z}_{EEG} will be larger after when compared to before movement (H_{1a}).	Pairwise t test	$N = 8$ ($d = 1.53$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)	Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).	The hypotheses will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .020$) and the associated Cohen's $d > d_{\text{SESOI}}$.
	\bar{z}_{EEG} post movement will be larger for the four-beat metre condition when compared to the three-beat metre condition (H_{1b}).	Mixed-model ANOVA (Movement Condition \times Session) followed by pairwise t test	$N = 20$ for the interaction effect ($f = 0.89$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$) and $N = 6$ for the simple effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)	Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).	

(Continued)

Movement will enhance the amplitude of metre frequencies in the clapping signal, and the four-beat metre condition will yield the most powerful effect.	$\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ will be larger after when compared to before the movement (H_{2a}).	Pairwise t test	$N = 6$ ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)	Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).	The hypothesis will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .020$) and the associated Cohen's $d > d_{\text{SESOI}}$.
	$\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ post movement will be larger for the four-beat metre condition when compared to the three-beat metre condition (H_{2b}).	Mixed-model ANOVA (Movement Condition \times Session) followed by pairwise t test	$N = 20$ for the interaction effect ($f = 0.89$; $\alpha = .02$; $1-\beta = .90$) and $N = 6$ for the simple effect ($d = 1.77$; $\alpha = .020$; $1-\beta = .90$)	Small telescopes approach ($d_{\text{SESOI}} = 0.47$).	

Note. Statistical power, planned analyses, and critical statistical tests for each research hypothesis. H = Hypothesis; RM ANOVA = Repeated-measures analysis of variance; SESOI = smallest effect size of interest.

Figure 1

Experimental Design and Material

Note. Panel A: Diagrammatic representation of the experimental design. Panel B: Rhythmic pattern with the overlaid drum sound that was used during the body-movement session in the three-beat (left) and four-beat (right) metre condition. Icon sources: ‘EEG’ by Aenne Briemann, ‘Clap hand’ by Ainul Muttaqin, and ‘Dancing’ by Jack (modified) from the Noun Project under CC BY 3.0 license.

Figure 2*Auditory Stimulus Analyses*

Note. Panel A: Spectrum of the acoustic stimuli. The grey bars represent the first and last frequency of the spectrum that were discarded (see “Sound Analysis” subsection). Panel B: Normalised spectrum amplitudes. Panel C: Averaged z scores. Each dot represents an individual frequency and the horizontal line represents the mean value. Three-beat metre related frequencies (i.e., 1.25 and 3.75 Hz) are highlighted in orange and four-beat metre related frequencies (i.e., and 0.83, 1.67, 3.33, and 4.17 Hz) in blue. a.u. = arbitrary unit.

Figure 3

Data-Processing Pipeline

Note. ICA = independent component analysis; FFT = fast-Fourier transform; freq. = frequency; ANOVA = analysis of variance. Icon sources: ‘Music and multimedia’ by Colourcreatype (modified), ‘Dancing’ by Jack (modified), ‘Clap hand’ by Ainul Muttaqin, ‘Head’ by Hunotika (modified), and ‘EEG’ by Aenne Brielmann (modified) from the Noun Project under CC BY 3.0 license.

Figure 4

Demographic Data and Familiarity with the Rhythmic Pattern

Note. Panel A: Demographic information (gender, age and country of origin). For the country of origin, the home country of the participant was used only when themselves have lived in this country for the first 15 years of their lives; otherwise, the home country of the participant's parents was used. DRC = Democratic Republic of Congo. Panel B: Ease, likeability, and familiarity with the rhythmic pattern. Data were collected at the end of the experimental session the using a 5-point Likert scale (see Supplementary File 1).

Figure 5

Neural Responses during the Pre- and Post-Movement Session

Note. Panel A: Time domain EEG signals averaged across participants and chunked over one pattern duration, shown for both sessions and conditions. EEG signals are overlaid on the stimulus envelope (in grey). Panel B: Magnitude spectra of neural responses averaged across participants separately for each session and condition. Three-beat and four-beat related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and metre-unrelated frequencies are shown in black. Time- and frequency-domain responses were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session, as experimental conditions only differed in the subsequent body-movement session. Panel C: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.

Figure 6

Behavioural Responses during the Pre- and Post-Movement Session

Note. Panel A: Inter-response intervals (IRIs) of hand-clapping responses for all participants before and after the body-movement session. Medians and quartiles are indicated by dots and vertical lines, respectively. In the pre-movement session, most participants clapped close to plausible metre periodicities (coloured horizontal lines), whereas responses in the post-movement session shifted towards the beat periodicities learned in each condition. Participants were sorted by their median IRI for each session separately. Panel B: Magnitude spectra of clapping responses averaged across participants for both sessions and conditions. Three-beat and four-beat metre-related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and meter-unrelated frequencies are highlighted in black. Note that IRIs and the magnitude spectra from all participants were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session as experimental conditions only differed in the body-movement session. Panel C: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots. *** $p < .001$.